

1. Equilibrium free energy calculations

Table 1: Equilibrium free energy results for all studied molecules (run 1). The corresponding ZINC database identifiers as well as the HiPen group are shown. ΔG_{eq} is the free energy difference between the MM and QML level of theory and is given as the mean of three sampling runs (in $k_{\text{B}}T$).

Cmp. Nr.	HiPen Nr.	ZINC ID	HiPen Group	ΔG_{eq}
1	2	00077329	Good	-940,543.72 \pm 0.08
2	3	00079729	Good	-2,105,811.31 \pm 0.09
3	4	00086442	Good	-656,584.53 \pm 0.11
4	5	00087557	Bad	-839,346.69 \pm 0.15
5	7	00107550	Good	-560,516.42 \pm 0.09
6	8	00107778	Ugly	-1,590,089.68 \pm 0.07
7	9	00123162	Ugly	-1,407,890.82 \pm 0.14
8	10	00133435	Good	-960,187.43 \pm 0.12
9	12	00140610	Good	-939,376.74 \pm 0.10
10	13	00164361	Good	-701,793.32 \pm 0.14
11	14	00167648	Good	-1,167,290.24 \pm 0.12
12	15	00169358	Good	-761,146.80 \pm 0.09
13	16	01755198	Bad	-604,674.39 \pm 0.11
14	17	01867000	Good	-730,760.51 \pm 0.09
15	18	03127671	Bad	-1,521,955.78 \pm 0.11
16	19	04344392	Bad	-1,347,288.63 \pm 0.14
17	20	04363792	Ugly	-2,972,461.56 \pm 0.11
18	21	06568023	Bad	-842,682.65 \pm 0.08
19	22	33381936	Bad	-

Table 2: Equilibrium free energy results for all studied molecules (run 2). The corresponding ZINC database identifiers as well as the HiPen group are shown. ΔG_{eq} is the free energy difference between the MM and QML level of theory and is given as the mean of three sampling runs (in $k_B T$).

Cmp. Nr.	HiPen Nr.	ZINC ID	HiPen Group	ΔG_{eq}
1	2	00077329	Good	$-940,543.77 \pm 0.08$
2	3	00079729	Good	$-2,105,811.46 \pm 0.09$
3	4	00086442	Good	$-656,584.63 \pm 0.11$
4	5	00087557	Bad	$-839,346.71 \pm 0.15$
5	7	00107550	Good	$-560,516.57 \pm 0.09$
6	8	00107778	Ugly	$-1,590,089.69 \pm 0.07$
7	9	00123162	Ugly	$-1,407,890.84 \pm 0.14$
8	10	00133435	Good	$-960,187.61 \pm 0.12$
9	12	00140610	Good	$-939,377.02 \pm 0.10$
10	13	00164361	Good	$-701,793.60 \pm 0.14$
11	14	00167648	Good	$-1,167,290.30 \pm 0.12$
12	15	00169358	Good	$-761,146.85 \pm 0.09$
13	16	01755198	Bad	$-604,674.27 \pm 0.11$
14	17	01867000	Good	$-730,760.61 \pm 0.09$
15	18	03127671	Bad	$-1,521,955.55 \pm 0.11$
16	19	04344392	Bad	$-1,347,288.81 \pm 0.14$
17	20	04363792	Ugly	$-2,972,461.54 \pm 0.11$
18	21	06568023	Bad	$-842,682.66 \pm 0.08$
19	22	33381936	Bad	-

Table 3: Equilibrium free energy results for all studied molecules (run 3). The corresponding ZINC database identifiers as well as the HiPen group are shown. ΔG_{eq} is the free energy difference between the MM and QML level of theory and is given as the mean of three sampling runs (in $k_B T$).

Cmp. Nr.	HiPen Nr.	ZINC ID	HiPen Group	ΔG_{eq}
1	2	00077329	Good	$-940,543.56 \pm 0.08$
2	3	00079729	Good	$-2,105,811.38 \pm 0.09$
3	4	00086442	Good	$-656,584.60 \pm 0.11$
4	5	00087557	Bad	$-839,346.85 \pm 0.15$
5	7	00107550	Good	$-560,516.31 \pm 0.09$
6	8	00107778	Ugly	$-1,590,089.73 \pm 0.07$
7	9	00123162	Ugly	$-1,407,890.94 \pm 0.14$
8	10	00133435	Good	$-960,187.55 \pm 0.12$
9	12	00140610	Good	$-939,377.03 \pm 0.10$
10	13	00164361	Good	$-701,793.45 \pm 0.14$
11	14	00167648	Good	$-1,167,290.09 \pm 0.12$
12	15	00169358	Good	$-761,146.91 \pm 0.09$
13	16	01755198	Bad	$-604,674.37 \pm 0.11$
14	17	01867000	Good	$-730,760.37 \pm 0.09$
15	18	03127671	Bad	$-1,521,955.55 \pm 0.11$
16	19	04344392	Bad	$-1,347,288.71 \pm 0.14$
17	20	04363792	Ugly	$-2,972,461.47 \pm 0.11$
18	21	06568023	Bad	$-842,682.65 \pm 0.08$
19	22	33381936	Bad	-

2. FEP

Table 4: FEP results (run 1). Bidirectional results $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ were derived from the BAR estimator; the unidirectional ones $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$ and $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$ with the exponential averaging method. Overlap between forward and backward energy distributions is given in percent. If the free energy estimate $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ deviates more than 1 k_BT from the equilibrium value $\Delta \bar{G}_{eq}$, the corresponding molecule is marked with an x.

Cmp. Nr.	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$	overlap ΔE (%)	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ diff. from $\Delta \bar{G}_{eq}$
1	-940,544.29 ± 0.13	-940,543.88 ± 0.89	940,547.41 ± 0.18	2.15	-
2	-2,105,811.59 ± 0.32	-2,105,805.98 ± 0.29	2,105,814.83 ± 0.62	0.39	-
3	-656,584.89 ± 0.86	-656,577.24 ± 0.66	656,592.37 ± 0.79	0.05	-
4	-839,344.82 ± 0.83	-839,324.59 ± 0.48	839,365.06 ± 0.67	0.00	x
5	-560,517.40 ± 0.30	-560,516.74 ± 0.98	560,521.76 ± 0.48	0.44	-
6	-1,590,089.92 ± 0.11	-1,590,089.16 ± 0.54	1,590,091.38 ± 0.36	3.03	-
7	-1,407,891.46 ± 1.08	-1,407,876.61 ± 0.70	1,407,906.31 ± 0.83	0.00	-
8	-960,188.16 ± 0.94	-960,180.19 ± 0.68	960,195.95 ± 0.82	0.04	-
9	-939,376.44 ± 0.37	-939,370.63 ± 0.57	939,380.73 ± 0.65	0.28	-
10	-701,791.02 ± 0.89	-701,779.18 ± 0.54	701,802.86 ± 0.71	0.00	x
11	-1,167,293.32 ± 0.88	-1,167,283.05 ± 0.58	1,167,303.56 ± 0.69	0.01	x
12	-761,147.12 ± 0.21	-761,143.18 ± 0.57	761,149.96 ± 0.45	0.86	-
13	-604,673.41 ± 0.41	-604,667.81 ± 0.42	604,678.32 ± 0.49	0.24	-
14	-730,760.53 ± 0.31	-730,756.23 ± 0.67	730,765.79 ± 0.37	0.42	-
15	-1,521,956.69 ± 0.58	-1,521,951.11 ± 0.56	1,521,958.50 ± 0.97	0.11	x
16	-1,347,293.59 ± 1.35	-1,347,282.87 ± 1.00	1,347,304.33 ± 0.92	0.01	x
17	-2,972,459.87 ± 0.55	-2,972,452.57 ± 0.29	2,972,465.84 ± 0.64	0.13	x
18	-842,682.68 ± 0.16	-842,688.20 ± 1.00	842,682.83 ± 0.91	1.53	-
19	-	-	-	-	-

Table 5: FEP results (run 2). Bidirectional results $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ were derived from the BAR estimator; the unidirectional ones $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$ and $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$ with the exponential averaging method. Overlap between forward and backward energy distributions is given in percent. If the free energy estimate $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ deviates more than 1 $k_B T$ from the equilibrium value ΔG_{eq} , the corresponding molecule is marked with an x.

Cmp. Nr.	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$	overlap ΔE (%)	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ diff. from $\Delta \bar{G}_{eq}$
1	-940,544.17 ± 0.13	-940,543.32 ± 0.67	940,546.37 ± 0.47	2.16	-
2	-2,105,811.56 ± 0.30	-2,105,805.72 ± 0.32	2,105,817.18 ± 0.48	0.40	-
3	-656,585.22 ± 0.62	-656,576.98 ± 0.65	656,593.79 ± 0.26	0.06	-
4	-839,346.47 ± 1.11	-839,327.22 ± 0.64	839,365.71 ± 0.91	0.00	-
5	-560,516.70 ± 0.32	-560,512.19 ± 0.47	560,522.15 ± 0.36	0.38	-
6	-1,590,089.89 ± 0.12	-1,590,089.44 ± 0.55	1,590,091.53 ± 0.38	2.80	-
7	-1,407,891.77 ± 1.17	-1,407,875.96 ± 0.95	1,407,907.58 ± 0.68	0.00	x
8	-960,187.84 ± 0.76	-960,179.65 ± 0.57	960,196.03 ± 0.60	0.06	-
9	-939,376.63 ± 0.42	-939,370.12 ± 0.40	939,382.21 ± 0.71	0.21	-
10	-701,794.21 ± 0.99	-701,777.92 ± 0.73	701,810.50 ± 0.67	0.00	-
11	-1,167,292.05 ± 1.10	-1,167,283.92 ± 0.98	1,167,300.82 ± 0.59	0.03	x
12	-761,147.31 ± 0.20	-761,144.47 ± 0.63	761,149.73 ± 0.44	1.03	-
13	-604,674.95 ± 0.60	-604,669.36 ± 0.86	604,678.37 ± 0.70	0.11	-
14	-730,760.13 ± 0.31	-730,759.47 ± 0.75	730,762.57 ± 0.91	0.40	-
15	-1,521,955.51 ± 0.66	-1,521,949.07 ± 0.62	1,521,961.27 ± 0.67	0.09	-
16	-1,347,291.64 ± 1.07	-1,347,276.80 ± 0.92	1,347,306.48 ± 0.55	0.00	x
17	-2,972,461.55 ± 0.82	-2,972,455.33 ± 0.91	2,972,466.78 ± 0.96	0.06	-
18	-842,682.89 ± 0.17	-842,688.20 ± 1.00	842,685.25 ± 0.47	1.41	-
19	-	-	-	-	-

Table 6: FEP results (run 3). Bidirectional results $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ were derived from the BAR estimator; the unidirectional ones $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$ and $\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$ with the exponential averaging method. Overlap between forward and backward energy distributions is given in percent. If the free energy estimate $\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ deviates more than 1 $k_B T$ from the equilibrium value ΔG_{eq} , the corresponding molecule is marked with an x.

Cmp. Nr.	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{MM,QML}$	$\Delta G_{FEP,uni}^{QML,MM}$	overlap ΔE (%)	$\Delta G_{FEP,bi}$ diff. from $\Delta \bar{G}_{eq}$
1	-940,544.03 ± 0.14	-940,543.02 ± 0.58	940,546.41 ± 0.49	1.97	-
2	-2,105,811.19 ± 0.28	-2,105,805.90 ± 0.36	2,105,814.76 ± 0.54	0.50	-
3	-656,584.06 ± 0.67	-656,575.74 ± 0.65	656,592.57 ± 0.42	0.06	-
4	-839,344.16 ± 0.97	-839,323.54 ± 0.79	839,364.78 ± 0.56	0.00	x
5	-560,516.89 ± 0.30	-560,516.75 ± 0.98	560,521.64 ± 0.38	0.45	-
6	-1,590,089.68 ± 0.11	-1,590,090.46 ± 0.78	1,590,091.13 ± 0.36	3.09	-
7	-1,407,893.23 ± 0.80	-1,407,877.81 ± 0.62	1,407,908.65 ± 0.51	0.00	x
8	-960,187.65 ± 0.89	-960,179.82 ± 0.73	960,195.76 ± 0.60	0.05	-
9	-939,376.78 ± 0.41	-939,371.65 ± 0.55	939,380.50 ± 0.67	0.23	-
10	-701,790.43 ± 1.14	-701,777.31 ± 0.56	701,803.55 ± 1.00	0.00	x
11	-1,167,291.74 ± 0.89	-1,167,282.77 ± 0.69	1,167,300.80 ± 0.59	0.03	x
12	-761,147.04 ± 0.21	-761,144.48 ± 0.57	761,149.85 ± 0.40	0.91	-
13	-604,674.44 ± 0.55	-604,669.31 ± 0.91	604,678.87 ± 0.85	0.13	-
14	-730,760.09 ± 0.29	-730,756.73 ± 0.62	730,762.59 ± 0.93	0.49	-
15	-1,521,955.42 ± 0.76	-1,521,948.50 ± 0.80	1,521,962.34 ± 0.66	0.07	-
16	-1,347,285.24 ± 1.09	-1,347,274.69 ± 0.45	1,347,295.68 ± 1.00	0.01	x
17	-2,972,462.06 ± 0.76	-2,972,452.87 ± 0.61	2,972,471.26 ± 0.57	0.03	-
18	-842,682.51 ± 0.15	-842,679.67 ± 0.45	842,682.80 ± 0.88	1.68	-
19	-	-	-	-	-

3. Endstate correction & torsion plots

3.1. ZINC00077329

Figure 1: Overlap plot for molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). The rows and columns correspond to the 11 λ states ranging from 0 (MM endstate) to 10 (QML endstate). The individual elements of the matrix $O_{i,j}$ denote the probabilities of observing a sample from state i in state j . The sum of each row and column is normalized to one.

Figure 2: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). (Top) Density plot of work and energy distributions with frequency on the ordinate and energy values on the x-axis. The MM \rightarrow QML NEQ work distribution, where initial coordinates were drawn from the MM equilibrium ensemble and switching was performed to the QML endstate potential, is shown in blue. The histogram for the reverse QML \rightarrow MM switching experiment is shown in green. The same pattern applies to energy distributions derived from FEP experiments, which are depicted in orange (MM \rightarrow QML) and red (QML \rightarrow MM), respectively. Both NEQ work distributions are a collection of 500 switching experiments in each direction. FEP experiments were repeated 5,000 times in each direction. (Middle) Comparison of NEQ and FEP free energy values to the equilibrium reference (in $k_B T$). Equilibrium and FEP values are collected from the first (out of three) repeats. NEQ results are the outcome of the 5 ps protocol. The labels are the same as in table 3.2 (main text). (Bottom) Cumulative standard deviation (in $k_B T$) of work and energy distributions recorded over 500 switches. The color code is identical to the one used in the top plot. The 1 and 2 $k_B T$ thresholds are shown as pink and purple dotted lines, respectively.

Figure 3: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). For details see figure 2.

Figure 4: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). For details see figure 2.

Figure 5: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00077329

Figure 6: Torsion profiles for the [3,4,6,7] dihedral angle of molecule 1 (ZINC00077329). On the lefthand side a violin plot of the observed torsion angles is shown. Black ticks correspond to individual samples. The right plot shows the kernel density estimates for the same data. Torsion angles are shown in radiant ranging from $-\pi$ to $+\pi$. Blue and orange data corresponds to torsion angles observed during three independent equilibrium simulations (for details see the Methods section) with the MM potential (blue) and the QML potential (orange). Torsion angles plotted in green and red indicate final conformations of switching trajectories (5 ps), either from MM to QML (red) or QML to MM (green) potential.

Torsion profile of ZINC00077329

Figure 7: Torsion profiles of molecule 1 (ZINC00077329) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00077329

Figure 8: Torsion profiles of molecule 1 (ZINC00077329) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00077329

Figure 9: Torsion profiles of molecule 1 (ZINC00077329) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.2. ZINC00079729

Figure 10: Overlap plot for molecule 2 (ZINC00079729). For details see figure 1.

Figure 11: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 2 (ZINC00079729). For details see figure 2.

Figure 12: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 2 (ZINC00079729). For details see figure 2.

Figure 13: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 2 (ZINC00079729). For details see figure 2.

Figure 14: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 2 (ZINC00079729). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00079729

Figure 15: Torsion profiles of molecule 2 (ZINC00079729) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00079729

Figure 16: Torsion profiles of molecule 2 (ZINC00079729) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00079729

Figure 17: Torsion profiles of molecule 2 (ZINC00079729) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00079729

Figure 18: Torsion profiles of molecule 2 (ZINC00079729) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.3. ZINC00086442

Figure 19: Overlap plot for molecule 3 (ZINC00086442). For details see figure 1.

Figure 20: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 3 (ZINC00086442). For details see figure 2.

Figure 21: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 3 (ZINC00086442). For details see figure 2.

Figure 22: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 3 (ZINC00086442). For details see figure 2.

Figure 23: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 3 (ZINC00086442). For details see figure 2.

3.4. ZINC00087557

Figure 24: Overlap plot for molecule 4 (ZINC00087557). For details see figure 1.

Figure 25: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 4 (ZINC00087557). For details see figure 2.

Figure 26: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 4 (ZINC00087557). For details see figure 2.

Figure 27: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 4 (ZINC00087557). For details see figure 2.

Figure 28: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 4 (ZINC00087557). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00087557

Figure 29: Torsion profiles of molecule 4 (ZINC00087557) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00087557

Figure 30: Torsion profiles of molecule 4 (ZINC00087557) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00087557

Figure 31: Torsion profiles of molecule 4 (ZINC00087557) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00087557

Figure 32: Torsion profiles of molecule 4 (ZINC00087557) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.5. ZINC00107550

Figure 33: Overlap plot for molecule 5 (ZINC00107550). For details see figure 1.

Figure 34: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 5 (ZINC00107550). For details see figure 2.

Figure 35: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 5 (ZINC00107550). For details see figure 2.

Figure 36: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 5 (ZINC00107550). For details see figure 2.

Figure 37: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 5 (ZINC00107550). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107550

Figure 38: Torsion profiles of molecule 5 (ZINC00107550) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107550

Figure 39: Torsion profiles of molecule 5 (ZINC00107550) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107550

Figure 40: Torsion profiles of molecule 5 (ZINC00107550) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107550

Figure 41: Torsion profiles of molecule 5 (ZINC00107550) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.6. ZINC00107778

Figure 42: Overlap plot for molecule 6 (ZINC00107778). For details see figure 1.

Figure 43: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 6 (ZINC00107778). For details see figure 2.

Figure 44: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 6 (ZINC00107778). For details see figure 2.

Figure 45: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 6 (ZINC00107778). For details see figure 2.

Figure 46: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 6 (ZINC00107778). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107778

Figure 47: Torsion profiles of molecule 6 (ZINC00107778) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107778

Figure 48: Torsion profiles of molecule 6 (ZINC00107778) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107778

Figure 49: Torsion profiles of molecule 6 (ZINC00107778) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00107778

Figure 50: Torsion profiles of molecule 6 (ZINC00107778) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.7. ZINC00123162

Figure 51: Overlap plot for molecule 7 (ZINC00123162). For details see figure 1.

Figure 52: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 7 (ZINC00123162). For details see figure 2.

Figure 53: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 7 (ZINC00123162). For details see figure 2.

Figure 54: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 7 (ZINC00123162). For details see figure 2.

Figure 55: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 7 (ZINC00123162). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00123162

Figure 56: Torsion profiles of molecule 7 (ZINC00123162) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00123162

Figure 57: Torsion profiles of molecule 7 (ZINC00123162) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00123162

Figure 58: Torsion profiles of molecule 7 (ZINC00123162) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00123162

Figure 59: Torsion profiles of molecule 7 (ZINC00123162) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.8. ZINC00133435

Figure 60: Overlap plot for molecule 8 (ZINC00133435). For details see figure 1.

Figure 61: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 8 (ZINC00133435). For details see figure 2.

Figure 62: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 8 (ZINC00133435). For details see figure 2.

Figure 63: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 8 (ZINC00133435). For details see figure 2.

Figure 64: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 8 (ZINC00133435). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00133435

Figure 65: Torsion profiles of molecule 8 (ZINC00133435) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00133435

Figure 66: Torsion profiles of molecule 8 (ZINC00133435) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00133435

Figure 67: Torsion profiles of molecule 8 (ZINC00133435) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00133435

Figure 68: Torsion profiles of molecule 8 (ZINC00133435) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.9. ZINC00140610

Figure 69: Overlap plot for molecule 9 (ZINC00140610). For details see figure 1.

Figure 70: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 9 (ZINC00140610). For details see figure 2.

Figure 71: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 9 (ZINC00140610). For details see figure 2.

Figure 72: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 9 (ZINC00140610). For details see figure 2.

Figure 73: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 9 (ZINC00140610). For details see figure 2.

3.10. ZINC00164361

Figure 74: Overlap plot for molecule 10 (ZINC00164361). For details see figure 1.

Figure 75: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 10 (ZINC00164361). For details see figure 2.

Figure 76: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 10 (ZINC00164361). For details see figure 2.

Figure 77: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 10 (ZINC00164361). For details see figure 2.

Figure 78: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 10 (ZINC00164361). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00164361

Figure 79: Torsion profiles of molecule 10 (ZINC00164361) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00164361

Figure 80: Torsion profiles of molecule 10 (ZINC00164361) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00164361

Figure 81: Torsion profiles of molecule 10 (ZINC00164361) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00164361

Figure 82: Torsion profiles of molecule 10 (ZINC00164361) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.11. ZINC00167648

Figure 83: Overlap plot for molecule 11 (ZINC00167648). For details see figure 1.

Figure 84: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 11 (ZINC00167648). For details see figure 2.

Figure 85: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 11 (ZINC00167648). For details see figure 2.

Figure 86: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 11 (ZINC00167648). For details see figure 2.

Figure 87: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 11 (ZINC00167648). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC00167648

Figure 88: Torsion profiles of molecule 11 (ZINC00167648) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00167648

Figure 89: Torsion profiles of molecule 11 (ZINC00167648) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00167648

Figure 90: Torsion profiles of molecule 11 (ZINC00167648) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC00167648

Figure 91: Torsion profiles of molecule 11 (ZINC00167648) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.12. ZINC00169358

Figure 92: Overlap plot for molecule 12 (ZINC00169358). For details see figure 1.

Figure 93: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 12 (ZINC00169358). For details see figure 2.

Figure 94: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 12 (ZINC00169358). For details see figure 2.

Figure 95: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 12 (ZINC00169358). For details see figure 2.

Figure 96: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 12 (ZINC00169358). For details see figure 2.

3.13. ZINC01755198

Figure 97: Overlap plot for molecule 13 (ZINC01755198). For details see figure 1.

Figure 98: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 13 (ZINC01755198). For details see figure 2.

Figure 99: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 13 (ZINC01755198). For details see figure 2.

Figure 100: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 13 (ZINC01755198). For details see figure 2.

Figure 101: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 13 (ZINC01755198). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC01755198

Figure 102: Torsion profiles of molecule 13 (ZINC01755198) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01755198

Figure 103: Torsion profiles of molecule 13 (ZINC01755198) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01755198

Figure 104: Torsion profiles of molecule 13 (ZINC01755198) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01755198

Figure 105: Torsion profiles of molecule 13 (ZINC01755198) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.14. ZINC01867000

Figure 106: Overlap plot for molecule 14 (ZINC01867000). For details see figure 1.

Figure 107: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 14 (ZINC01867000). For details see figure 2.

Figure 108: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 14 (ZINC01867000). For details see figure 2.

Figure 109: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 14 (ZINC01867000). For details see figure 2.

Figure 110: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 14 (ZINC01867000). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC01867000

Figure 111: Torsion profiles of molecule 14 (ZINC01867000) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01867000

Figure 112: Torsion profiles of molecule 14 (ZINC01867000) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01867000

Figure 113: Torsion profiles of molecule 14 (ZINC01867000) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC01867000

Figure 114: Torsion profiles of molecule 14 (ZINC01867000) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.15. ZINC03127671

Figure 115: Overlap plot for molecule 15 (ZINC03127671). For details see figure 1.

Figure 116: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 15 (ZINC03127671). For details see figure 2.

Figure 117: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 15 (ZINC03127671). For details see figure 2.

Figure 118: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 15 (ZINC03127671). For details see figure 2.

Figure 119: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 15 (ZINC03127671). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC03127671

Figure 120: Torsion profiles of molecule 15 (ZINC03127671) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC03127671

Figure 121: Torsion profiles of molecule 15 (ZINC03127671) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC03127671

Figure 122: Torsion profiles of molecule 15 (ZINC03127671) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC03127671

Figure 123: Torsion profiles of molecule 15 (ZINC03127671) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.16. ZINC04344392

Figure 124: Overlap plot for molecule 16 (ZINC04344392). For details see figure 1.

Figure 125: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 16 (ZINC04344392). For details see figure 2.

Figure 126: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 16 (ZINC04344392). For details see figure 2.

Figure 127: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 16 (ZINC04344392). For details see figure 2.

Figure 128: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 16 (ZINC04344392). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC04344392

Figure 129: Torsion profiles of molecule 16 (ZINC04344392) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04344392

Figure 130: Torsion profiles of molecule 16 (ZINC04344392) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04344392

Figure 131: Torsion profiles of molecule 16 (ZINC04344392) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04344392

Figure 132: Torsion profiles of molecule 16 (ZINC04344392) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.17. ZINC04363792

Figure 133: Overlap plot for molecule 17 (ZINC04363792). For details see figure 1.

Figure 134: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 17 (ZINC04363792). For details see figure 2.

Figure 135: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 17 (ZINC04363792). For details see figure 2.

Figure 136: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 17 (ZINC04363792). For details see figure 2.

Figure 137: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 17 (ZINC04363792). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC04363792

Figure 138: Torsion profiles of molecule 17 (ZINC04363792) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04363792

Figure 139: Torsion profiles of molecule 17 (ZINC04363792) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04363792

Figure 140: Torsion profiles of molecule 17 (ZINC04363792) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC04363792

Figure 141: Torsion profiles of molecule 17 (ZINC04363792) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

3.18. ZINC06568023

Figure 142: Overlap plot for molecule 18 (ZINC06568023). For details see figure 1.

Figure 143: 5 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 18 (ZINC06568023). For details see figure 2.

Figure 144: 10 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 18 (ZINC06568023). For details see figure 2.

Figure 145: 20 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 18 (ZINC06568023). For details see figure 2.

Figure 146: 50 ps NEQ switching and FEP results for molecule 18 (ZINC06568023). For details see figure 2.

Torsion profile of ZINC06568023

Figure 147: Torsion profiles of molecule 18 (ZINC06568023) before and after the 5 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC06568023

Figure 148: Torsion profiles of molecule 18 (ZINC06568023) before and after the 10 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC06568023

Figure 149: Torsion profiles of molecule 18 (ZINC06568023) before and after the 20 ps switch. For details see figure 6.

Torsion profile of ZINC06568023

Figure 150: Torsion profiles of molecule 18 (ZINC06568023) before and after the 50 ps switch. For details see figure 6.